

Methylation of 4: A mixture of **4** ($R_1=R_2=R_3=Me$; 1.5 g), methyl iodide (0.8 ml) and absolute alcohol (5 ml) were refluxed for 1.5 h. On cooling, the isolated solid was reprecipitated with dry ether (1 g), m.p. 205° (Found: N, 12.61; S, 19.24. $C_7H_{13}N_3S_2 \cdot HI$ requires: N, 12.71; S, 19.33%). It was identified as 1,6,6-trimethyl-4-methylmercapto-2-thio-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine hydriodide (**5**, $R_4=Me$).

Benzylation of 4: A mixture of **4** ($R_1=R_2=R_3=Me$), benzyl chloride and sodium hydroxide in molar proportions in alcohol under similar reaction conditions as described above gave **5** ($R_4=benzyl$), m.p. 116°.

5-Alkylidene-1-aryl/alkyl-2,4-dithiobiuret hydrochloride (3): Methyl dithiobiuret (**1**, $R=Me$; 3 g) was dissolved in acetone (30 ml) and the solution cooled in ice. Through the cooled solution was passed a dry stream of hydrogen chloride when **3** (4.2 g) was obtained, m.p. 169°. It showed no depression in m.p. with the product obtained by the reaction of ethyl chloroformate with methyl dithiobiuret. Its spectrum (KBr) showed perfect superimposability. The other products obtained are given in Table I. Compounds **3** obtained by the above procedure were converted into **4** by alkali as described earlier, which also showed no depression in m.m.p and the ir spectra being superimposable.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support. Thanks are also due to Prof. V. S. Darshane, Head, Chemistry Department and to Prof. A. N. Inamdar, Director, Institute of Science, for facilities.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of 2-Phthalimidomethyl-3-(3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-substituted/6,8-disubstituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines

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Manuscript received 28 November 1989, revised 12 April 1990,
accepted 3 July 1990

SEVERAL 2,3-disubstituted-4-quinazolines¹ and methaqualone, 2-methyl-2-(*o*-tolyl)-3H-4-quinazolinone have been reported to possess CNS activities. Aminomethyl pharmacophores in many compounds^{3,4} yielded the pharmacologically active compounds while profound anticonvulsant activity was observed in morpholines⁵ and piperidines⁶. It was therefore considered of interest to synthesise some newer quinazolinones (Scheme 1) and screen them for their CNS activity.

Compounds **4e-h** were prepared by condensing **3a-d** with 4-aminophenol. **3a-d** intermediates were obtained by reacting substituted-anthranilic acids with phthalimidocetyl chloride in dry pyridine at 0–5°. Compounds **5i-w** were obtained by Mannich reactions of **4e-h** with different secondary amines.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The reactions were followed by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 and 177 or 137 spectrophotometers and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6$) on a R-32 instrument (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

5-Bromo-⁷, 3,5-dibromo-⁷ and 5-iodoanthranilic acids⁸ and phthalimidoacetic acids⁹ were prepared according to the known methods.

2-Phthalimidomethyl-6-substituted/6,8-disubstituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-benzoxazines (3a-d): To a solution of substituted anthranilic acid (0.001 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) at 0°, was added phthalimidocetyl chloride (0.001 mol) slowly in small portions keeping the temperature at 0–5°. It was shaken for 1 h at this temperature and kept overnight at room temperature. Cold dilute hydrochloric acid was then added to it with shaking and the separated crystalline mass was washed with cold water, treated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and washed again with cold water, air-dried and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (60%): **a** ($X_1=X_2=H$), m.p. 235–40°; **b** ($X_1=Br, X_2=H$), m.p. 110°; **c** ($X_1=X_2=Br$), m.p. 204–05°; **d** ($X_1=I, X_2=H$), m.p. 223–28°.

Scheme 1

2-Phthalimidomethyl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-substituted/6,8-disubstituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines (4e-h): A mixture of benzoxazines (3a-d) and 4-aminophenol (0.001 mol) dissolved in dry pyridine (10 ml), was refluxed for 6-12 h. It was then cooled and poured over crushed ice containing hydrochloric acid, and the resulting solid was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (60-75%): **4e** (X₁=X₂=H), m.p. 230-32°; **f** (X₁=Br, X₂=H), m.p. 77°; **g** (X₁=X₂=Br), m.p. 210°; **h** (X₁=I, X₂=H), m.p. 215°; ν_{\max} 2900 (CH methyl), 1785 (ArCONCOAr), 1720 (quinazolinone C=O), 1620 (C=N) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (Ar); δ 4.50-4.9 (2H, s, CH₂) and 7.90-7.0 (10H, m, ArH).

2-Phthalimidomethyl-3-(3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-substituted/6,8-disubstituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines (5i-w): The quinazolinone (4e-h; 0.001 mol) and formalin (37%; 0.003 mol) were refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for 1 h. An appropriate secondary amine (0.001 mol) was then added to it and the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 10-12 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the residue was recrystallised from the appropriate solvent, (70-75%), ν_{\max} 3300-3200br (OH), 3000 (CH methyl), 1780 (ArCONCOAr), 1715 (quinazolinone C=O), 1610 (C=N) and 1590 cm⁻¹ (Ar); **5p** δ 1.15 (2H, m, CH₂-NR₁R₂), 2.5-2.3 (4H, m, CH₂-N-CH₂ of morpholino), 3.85-3.50 (4H, m, CH₂-O-CH₂ of morpholino), 4.4-4.35 (2H, s, CH₂ at position-2) and 8.0-6.9 (10H, m, ArH).

Pharmacological studies: Five compounds were evaluated for acute toxicity and gross behavioural effects. The gross behavioural effects of all the compounds were evaluated¹⁰ at 1/5th the ALD₅₀ dose level. The compounds were also tested for their anticonvulsant and anorexigenic activities using the standard methods¹⁰. The compounds were least toxic with high ALD₅₀>1000 mg/kg. Compound **5o** had an ALD₅₀ of 261 mg/kg. At 1/5th of ALD₅₀ the compound did not show any significant activity. The loss of activity in these compounds could possibly be explained by the contention that these compounds were not acting on the receptors sensitive to active moieties due to change in the stereochemistry of the molecule since the receptor sites are highly stereoselective.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5*

Compd no.	NR ₁ R ₂	X ₁	X ₂	M p	Mol formula
5i	Dimethylamino	H	H	220	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄
5j	Diethylamino	H	H	195-97	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄
5k	Piperidino	H	H	170	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄
5l	Morpholino	H	H	175-80	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅
5m	Dimethylamino	Br	Br	170-75	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄
5n	Diethylamino	Br	Br	125	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄
5o	Piperidino	Br	Br	129-30	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄
5p	Morpholino	Br	Br	168-70	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₅
5q	Dimethylamino	Br	H	145-50	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ O ₄
5r	Diethylamino	Br	H	169-70	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ BrN ₄ O ₄

(Table 1 contd.)

s	Piperidino	Br	H	230	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ BrN ₄ O ₄
t	Morpholino	Br	H	122-25	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ BrN ₄ O ₅
u	Diethylamino	I	H	175	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ IN ₄ O ₄
v	Piperidino	I	H	222-24	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ IN ₄ O ₄
w	Morpholino	I	H	145	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ IN ₄ O ₅

*All compounds showed satisfactory N analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for the bioassay and to Mr. V. N. Bhalla, Senior Technical Assistant, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for technical assistance.

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Synthesis of 4,6-Bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-aryl-pyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols as Potential Antifeedants

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Manuscript received 18 April 1990, accepted 26 July 1990

PYRAZOLE and pyrazoline derivatives exhibit a variety of pharmacological activities¹. 3,4-Diaryl-1-phenylcarbamoyl- Δ^2 -pyrazolines possess promising insecticidal activity². These considerations have prompted us to synthesise some 4,6-bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-arylpyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols with a view to evaluate their antifeedant activity.

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-acetylacetophenone³ (**1**) was condensed with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of 60% aqueous KOH to yield the corresponding dichalcones (**2a-g**), which were characterised by comparison with authentic samples⁴ and through other test. The dichalcones (**2a-g**) on being

refluxed with 95% hydrazine hydrate and on usual workup of the reaction mixture gave the corresponding 4,6-bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-arylpyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols (**3a-g**) in good yields (62-75%). As a representative case, the spectral identification of 4,6-bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-phenylpyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinol (**3a**) has been discussed. Compound **3a** revealed ν_{max} at 3 320 (NH), 3 330-3 500br (OH) and 1 635 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 3.06 (2H, dd, $J_{4'\text{H}_B, 4'\text{H}_A}$ 18 Hz, $J_{4'\text{H}_B, 5'\text{H}}$ 5 Hz, H_B-4'), 3.47 (2H, dd, $J_{4'\text{H}_A, 4'\text{H}_B}$ 18 Hz, $J_{4'\text{H}_A, 5'\text{H}}$ 12 Hz, H_A-4'), 4.86 (2H, dd, $J_{5'\text{H}, 4'\text{H}_A}$ 12 Hz, $J_{5'\text{H}, 4'\text{H}_B}$ 5 Hz, H-5), 6.63 (1H, s, H-2) and 6.90 (1H, s, H-5), 7.33 (10H, m, C-5' phenyl rings) and 2.14 (br d, NH)⁵; m/z 398 (100%) consistent with its molecular formula C₂₄H₂₂O₂N₄, 397 [M-H] (32%), 321 (62%) (loss of phenyl due to α -cleavage), 294 (10%) (loss of styrene moiety), 190 (8%) (loss of two styrene moieties), 118 (pyrazoline ring cleavage) characteristic of Δ^2 -pyrazolines⁶, 310 (23%), 216 (13%), 104 (17%), 103 (5%) and 77 (12%). UV spectral data are given in Table 1.

All the compounds (**3**) were tested for their anti-feedant activity by the non-choice test method⁷ using 6 h prestarved fourth instar larvae of *Spodoptera litura*. The results are shown in Table 1. Compound **3e** exhibited highest antifeedant activity.

Experimental

Dichalcones (2a-g). *General procedure:* A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) was kept at room temperature for 12 h with 60% aqueous KOH (10 ml). The product, obtained on dilution and acidification with dilute HCl was subjected to column chromatography.